

INTERACTION BETWEEN METALLIC MICRO-FASTENERS AND CARBON-FIBRE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Abstract

A method for analysing load transfer in novel metal-composite joints is presented. Hybrid penetrative reinforcement (HYPER) uses small pins, protruding from the metallic part, to increase fracture toughness but manufacturing can cause fibre distortion and resin rich zones in the carbon-fibre laminate (CFRP). Conventional finite element approaches for modelling CFRP are considered to be low fidelity as individual plies are homogenised and hence are not representative if fibres do not remain straight. A high fidelity finite element model of a micro-fastener within a CFRP unit cell is developed. It was found that, for a cross-ply laminate, $[0/90]_N$, a low fidelity model would transmit the greatest load into the 0 degree plies. However, when accounting for the fibre distortion and resin rich zones, the load transmitted through the 90 degree plies was actually higher than that transferred by the 0 degree plies - which were almost 50% more compliant than predicted by the conventional model.

Nomenclature

L, H	= Half-length/height of a unit cell
h	= Fibre path offset in y-axis
R	= Radius of fastener
x, y, z	= Cartesian position within unit cell
x', y'	= Position on unrotated unit cell
V_f	= Local fibre volume fraction
$V_f^0, \bar{V}_f, \hat{V}_f$	= Nominal, mean, maximum vol. fraction
α	= Polar coordinate on unrotated unit cell
θ	= Local fibre orientation
ϕ	= Undistorted fibre angle of each ply

1. Introduction

Despite the increased use of carbon-fibre reinforced composites (CFRP) for aerospace and automotive structures, poor through-thickness strength and the low heat resistance of the resin matrix results in metals still being selected for a significant proportion of components. Conventionally, joining these materials is achieved with bolting or riveting but these techniques are fundamentally flawed as drilling through continuous fibres reduces their load carrying capability and creates stress concentrations. Several novel technologies are under development as potential alternatives to traditional mechanical fastening methods and, by exploiting the latest manufacturing processes, can hopefully improve the integration of metals and CFRP [1-6]. Analogous to Z-pinning or hybrid composite-composite joining methods, through-thickness reinforcement with pins can improve fracture toughness of hybrid joints [1]. Arrays of pins can be built onto a metal component with a laser surface treatment [2] or additive manufacture (AM) [3-5] or pre-fabricated and attached by arc welding (CMT) [6].

Hybrid Penetrative Reinforcement (HYPER) is one such technology being developed by EADS Innovation Works [3]. Titanium pins can be built onto a stock component using AM which provides unrivalled capability for optimisation of the pin/array geometry compared to CMT. The pins are embedded into an uncured CFRP laminate using an ultrasonic horn and the assembly is then co-cured; Fig. 1 shows an assembled joint. The pins create a mechanical interlock whilst the epoxy resin matrix of the laminate provides adhesion. The authors have recently reported experimental investigations into the quasi-static and fatigue performance of HYPER joints as well as non-destructive inspection techniques that can be used to detect damage [4, 5].

It was shown that the pins delay the initiation of failure, retard the propagation of damage and provide a significant increase in the ultimate tensile strength (up to 650%) compared to an unpinned benchmark joint.

Fig. 1. Section of baseline single-lap HYPER joint coupon showing pin array. Adherends are nominally 5mm thick. Not to scale.

Although these results were promising, the coupon tests used a baseline pin/array design that is thought to be sub-optimal. As already stated, AM provides huge potential for optimisation of this joining technology (e.g. pin radii, height and spacing) but to date, little work has been conducted in this area. Tu et al. completed a preliminary optimisation study of COMELD joints [2], however, this was completed with a two dimensional (through thickness) model and hence did not account for any in-plane distortion. Prior to optimisation of the HYPER geometry, a new higher fidelity finite element (FE) modelling approach is required in order to more accurately account for the interaction of the pins and the CFRP laminate. This interaction is critical to the load transfer within these joints and to ensure accurate simulation of both the failure mode(s) and strength. Existing FE models for HYPER have been constructed with individual plies represented by homogenised layers [7]. This is overly simplistic and inaccurate because during manufacture, embedding of the pins can result in fibre distortion (waviness) and resin rich zones around the pins - see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. X-ray tomography showing a plan view section of four pins and resin rich zones (black).

The objective of this work was to develop a high fidelity FE model and investigate pin-fibre interaction. This work forms a preliminary stage in the development of new multi-scale capability for HYPER joints. It is believed that a multi-scale FE approach will have adequate fidelity to yield accurate results yet retain computational efficiency so that optimisation of key design parameters can be conducted.

2. Background

A review of the literature revealed that a comparable approach had been utilised by Gunnion et al. [8] to characterise Z-pinned CFRP laminates. Similarly to HYPER joint manufacture, embedding Z-pins creates in-plane waviness and resin rich zones in reinforced areas. Unfortunately, due to the shape of these regions, when multiple plies are stacked together, a very fine mesh is required in order to avoid any discontinuities. To avoid any discontinuities, Gunnion et al. used voxels (three dimensional pixels) to model a Z-pinned representative volume element (RVE). By using a mesh of regularly structured, quadrilateral elements, multiple plies could be stacked together and mesh discontinuities avoided even with a large element size. Geometric and numerical accuracy was still largely dependent on the refinement of the mesh but it was shown that acceptable homogenisation of the RVE could be achieved with large computational savings. This method was suitable for this homogenisation task as the pins were small compared to the unit cell. Loads transmitted through the pin were neglected and boundary conditions were applied to the external edges of the RVE. This voxel approach could not be used for HYPER as the pin aspect ratio and material results in them being stiffer than Z-pins and transferring a significant proportion of applied loads. Examples of pin and array geometry are listed in Table 1.

Type	Diameter (mm)	Penetration in CFRP	Density by Area
Z-Pins	0.3 - 0.5	100 %	1 - 6 %
HYPER	0.9 - 1.8	72 %	4 - 13 %
COMELD	0.8	50 %	~ 45 %

Table 1. Comparative geometry of three penetrative joining technologies.

Upscaling in the same way as Gunnion et al. would not accurately model any bearing load transferred through the HYPER pin to the surrounding material. The bearing load induced on the CFRP by a cylindrical pin/fastener should be maximal at the centre of the contact face and decrease to zero at the edges due to the reduction in contact angle. In Gunnion's model, because the mesh is formed of regularly spaced quadrahedral elements, for loads in the primary axes (x or y), the pin elements always contact the surrounding material perpendicularly. As a result, the load would be uniformly distributed across the diameter of the pin and the induced stress at the edges of the pin artificially high. Therefore, it is essential to model the pin/hole with greater geometric accuracy.

3. Overview of Modelling

The goal of the work presented in this paper is to determine whether a low fidelity approach (homogenisation of individual plies) should be used for modelling of HYPER joints or if a more accurate representation of the pin-fibre interaction is required. Hence, it is not necessary to model at coupon level at this stage and a new unit cell model is proposed. Although baseline coupon designs typically use a 6x6 array of pins, for the purposes of this study it is assumed that only a single row of pins exist in the loading direction. This configuration is more severe for the laminate as the entire load is transmitted through bearing and stress concentrations at the edges of the fastener are higher. Additional unit cells would have to be modelled in series to account for the load bypass around the pin.

It is also assumed that longitudinal loads are predominantly transferred below the pin head thus, only the lower section of the pin is modelled; see Fig. 3a-b. Although HYPER pins have a complex tapered profile, it is assumed that they are cylindrical and that there is no variation in diameter through the thickness of the laminate. For simplicity, the non-linear geometric (rotational) effects of a single-lap joint are ignored. The metallic adherend is not modelled and it is assumed that the pin receives an in-plane load; Fig. 3c. The inclusion of coupled, multi-axis loads/moments is beyond the scope of the paper.

Figure 3d shows a plan view of the unit cell. Although only a single row of pins is modelled in the loading direction, periodic boundaries are enforced to maintain continuity with adjacent cells across width of the coupon. The pin diameter was chosen to be one-third of the width of the unit cell ($R/H = 0.333$). This ratio is known to be an optimal compromise between bearing and net-section stress for a wide range of layups [9]. This ratio is comparable to the baseline HYPER joint design.

Fig. 3. a) Partial section of single-lap HYPER joint coupon showing pins. b) Only a single row of pins was included and the shaft is modelled without the head. c) In-plane loading is applied to pin. d) Plan view of unit cell showing boundary conditions (transverse displacement constrained).

The pin-fibre interaction was assessed based on the in-plane load distribution and compliance of two individual ply orientations: firstly, fibres aligned with the load direction (0 degrees) and secondly, fibres perpendicular to the load (90 degrees). These test cases were chosen as they should have the greatest and least membrane stiffness respectively (in the loading direction). These tests could be considered artificial as, typically, a laminate would not be constructed with these plies in isolation. However, these simulations emphasise the comparative differences between orthogonal fibre orientations. The model is conservative as peak stresses would actually be lower (if using a quasi-isotropic layup) due to compatibility between plies of different orientations through-thickness. A three-dimensional analysis is beyond the scope of the paper and will form part of the future work. As through thickness effects were neglected, the unit cell was modelled in 2D and plane strain elements were used. Analyses of mesh sensitivity and element selection are presented in the Results. Both test cases were also modelled using a conventional low fidelity “straight fibre” (SF) model as a benchmark - see Table 2 and Fig. 4. All models/tests were constructed and solved with the commercial FE package ABAQUS [10].

	Fibre Distortion & Resin Rich Zones	Variation in V_f
Model SF		
Benchmark Low Fidelity	No (Straight fibres)	No
Model DF		
New Approach High Fidelity	Yes	Yes

Table 2. Details of model configurations.

Fig. 4. Examples of straight and distorted fibres in the two models, SF and DF respectively. Resin shown black, $\phi = 0$.

3.1 Calculation of Fibre Distortion

It was assumed that in-plane fibre waviness could be represented with the sinusoidal function:

$$y = R \left(1 - \frac{h}{H} \right) \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2L} \right) + h \quad (1)$$

where R is a given pin radius and h is an offset that also governs the decay of the amplitude. It is also assumed that the fibre distortion has fully minimised at $x = \pm L$ and $y = \pm H$, the full height and width of the unit cell although a more rapid decay in either axis could easily be implemented. The local fibre angle, θ can be found at any cell position (x,y) by rearranging Eqn. 1, solving for h and then substituting this value into the differential of Eqn. 1. This formulation is only valid for $h \geq 0$. Between this limit and $y = 0$, θ is not calculated as the element is assumed to be 100% resin if it is not within the radius of the pin. These are the grey regions in Fig. 5. Below the centreline of the cell, a symmetry condition was applied ($y = -y$) so that θ could be determined in an identical manner to the upper half of the cell. This formulation is not mesh dependent and could be completed for any mesh as long as the nodal positions can be extracted - the local fibre angle can then be calculated at that the centroid of each element.

3.2 System Transformation

For non-zero ply angles ($\phi \neq 0$), a polar transformation was used to rotate the system $\pm 90^\circ$. If $y \geq x \tan \phi$, the polar position on an unrotated system was found by:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y}{x} \right) - \phi, & x \geq 0 \\ \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y}{x} \right) - \phi + 90, & x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The polar coordinates on the unrotated system are then reverted back to a Cartesian position (x, y) and θ calculated as previously described. On the original (rotated) system, the true local fibre angle is found with the addition of ϕ , as shown in Fig. 6. If the unrotated local position $y < x \tan \phi$, i.e. $y' < 0$, a symmetry condition can again be used to calculate the fibre orientation but, for this case, two conditions must be applied; $y = -y$ and $x = -x$.

Fig. 5 Diagram of RVE showing a single, unrotated ply ($\phi = 0$) with two arbitrary fibre paths. Resin rich zones shown in grey.

Fig. 6. Decay length/height remain constant regardless of ply angle (ϕ) thus, in shaded regions, there is no fibre distortion ($\theta = \phi$).

3.3 Change in Fibre Volume Fraction

Unlike Gunnion et al. [8], a micro-scale materials model was also incorporated to account for the local changes in fibre volume fraction and the resultant modification to mechanical properties due to fibre distortion. This was included due to the density of the pins (and hence distortion) being greater than a Z-pinned joint; see Table 1. The analytical fibre-resin model of Luciano and Barbero was used [11]. It is assumed that the volume of fibre in a strip of Δx is maintained when distortion is induced (see Fig. 7) and thus, the mean volume fraction, \bar{V}_f in the new “compressed” strip was given by Eqn. 3.

$$\bar{V}_f(x) = \frac{V_f^0}{1 - \frac{\Delta y}{H}} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta y = R \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2L} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$V_f(x, y) = A(H - y) + V_f^0 \quad (5)$$

$$A = \frac{2(V_f^0 - \bar{V}_f)}{H - \Delta y} \quad (6)$$

The fibre waviness minimises by $y = H$ (Eqn. 1) so the local fibre volume fraction, V_f would also have returned to the nominal value, V_f^0 at this limit. Furthermore, it is assumed that there is a linear variation in V_f between the nominal and maximum values, as given by Eqn. 5 and shown in Fig. 7. It should be noted it is possible for Eqn. 3 to yield $V_f > 1.0$ which indicates that the ply would have to change thickness to maintain compatibility.

Fig. 7. Plan view of half a unit cell with a linear distribution of local fibre volume fraction assumed with respect to y-axis position.

However, to simplify the geometry of the model, it was desirable for the thickness of all plies to remain constant. In addition, Luciano and Barbero's model [11] assumes that the fibres are square packed and it can be shown that $\hat{V}_f = 78.5\%$ for this configuration – thus, an upper bound was set at $\hat{V}_f = 78.5\%$. Both fibres and resin are modelled as isotropic linearly elastic materials [12] and no failure criterion is applied – this will be considered in the future work programme.

Fig. 8. Plot of volume fraction variation within a unit cell - including regions that exceed the volume fraction upper bound ($\phi = 0$).

Fig. 9. Percentage of elements that exceed the volume fraction upper bound for a range of pin radii.

Figure 8 shows the regions of a unit cell exceeding the volume fraction upper bound ($R/H = 0.333$, $\phi = 0$). For a pin diameter for one-third the unit cell, 11.3% of elements assigned a revised volume fraction exceed the upper bound of 78.5%. This value would vary depending on the pin radius and ply orientation – Fig. 9 shows a comparison.

3.4 Integration of Pre-Processing

Automated pre-processing within ABAQUS can be realised in a number of ways. It is possible to write an input file directly using a text editor. This process can therefore be automated in most programming languages with basic input/output commands. This approach would totally bypass the “CAE” graphical user interface (GUI) and would be extremely efficient for geometrically simplistic models (e.g. if nodal positions and element connectivity can be easily formulated).

Fig. 10. Information transfer within ABAQUS.

For this model, due to the more complex geometry, it was essential to take advantage of the software's advanced CAD and meshing capabilities. This was achieved with the Python Development Environment. Upon submitting a model to the solver, the input file still needs to be written so this approach incurs an additional step for each perturbation of the model; see Fig. 10. To avoid compromising the speed of the pre-processor with unnecessary visualisations in the GUI, Python scripts were run using the DOS command line interface.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Mesh Refinement

The mesh density would determine the geometric accuracy with which the resin zone would be modelled – Fig. 11 shows two examples. Hence, a mesh sensitivity study was completed for Model DF before stress distributions and ply compliance was evaluated. This study determined the number/size of elements that would be used for each of the two test cases to ensure an efficient compromise between computational speed and accuracy.

Fig. 11. Coarse and fine meshes, element size 2.5% and 1.0% of unit cell respectively. Resin zones are shown in black ($\phi = 0$).

Five in-plane mesh refinements were made and element seed size was set as a percentage of the unit cell width (2.5%-0.5%). Varying the mesh density resulted in a change to the stiffness of the model so in order to compare stress distributions a constant axial stress was applied. This was arbitrarily chosen as 100MPa for the 0 degree ply and 50MPa for the 90 degree ply. The Laminate Analysis Programme [13] was used to ensure these loads were well within the nominal strength of the plies so that simulations would not induce failure and a linear analysis would remain accurate.

Element Size (%)	Total Elements	Solution Time
2.50	1416	0:00:49
1.25	5704	0:07:04
1.00	8978	0:13:28
0.75	15597	0:38:53
0.50	35352	3:06:20

Table 3. Comparison of computation times for five mesh densities using CPE4R elements. Sizes are a percentage of unit cell width. Solution times are shown in hours, minutes and seconds.

The model was run on an Intel-i7 (2.80GHz) desktop computer with 8Gb of RAM - computation times are shown in Table 3. It can be seen that the time required to solve the model increases exponentially as the element size is reduced. It was found that the solution time is dominated by the time required to process the input file and thus refinements will be made to the pre-processor in the future work programme.

Comparison was made of the peak net-section stresses (σ_x along the line $x = 0$) to select an appropriate mesh density. Variation in peak stress was found to reduce with increased mesh density. With an element size of 0.75%, there was a difference of only 3.5% in peak stress compared to a mesh size of 0.5% yet the computation time was reduced by 79.9%. Therefore, it was decided that a mesh size of 0.75% provided a good compromise between speed and accuracy and was used for all subsequent analyses. In addition, it was found that there was good correlation between linear and quadratic (reduce integration) plane strain elements; CPE4R and CPE8R respectively. As a result, linear elements were used as they offered a comparative reduction in computation time.

4.2 Comparison of Models

The objective was to investigate the location and magnitude of the peak stresses in both the high and low fidelity models. The displacement of the pin was also used to calculate and evaluate an equivalent ply stiffness for each model.

4.2.1 Stress Distributions

Figures 12-14 compare stress contours of Models SF and DF for each of the two test cases. The scaling varies between each figure but is identical for each pair of sub-plots so the two models could be directly compared. In both test cases, the low fidelity model (SF) generated peak stresses that were overly high and incorrectly located compared to the high fidelity model (DF). As a result, a conventional modelling approach is overly conservative and the model would predict early failure of the laminate if a failure criterion were used.

Fig. 12. Axial stress (σ_x) for the 0 degree ply. Peak tensile stresses in Model SF are located at the top and bottom of the pin. The maxima in Model DF are located in identical positions but are 67% lower in magnitude. The influence of fibre orientation on the load path can also be seen.

Fig. 13. Transverse tensile stress (σ_y) for the 0 degree ply, compressive stresses excluded for clarity (black regions). Model SF shows two regions of artificially high stress to the right of pin. High stress at tip of resin zone (DF) was due to fibres being forced apart by the “wedge” of resin.

Fig. 14. Axial stress (σ_x) for the 90 degree ply. Model SF again exhibits artificially high stresses. The maxima in Model DF can be seen at the tips the resin zone. The compression zone is also narrower due to the finite contact region between pin and fibres.

4.2.2 Assessment of Laminate Compliance

The displacement of the pin (in x) was also recorded for each of the models and test cases so that an equivalent stiffness (K_x) could be calculated. Table 4 shows these stiffnesses, normalised with respect to the 0 degree ply (Model SF). It can be seen that accurately modelling the fibre distortion in a 0 degree ply reduces the stiffness by almost a half. Conversely, the high fidelity model of a 90 degree ply showed a 3.6% increase in stiffness compared to Model SF. More significantly, Model DF was actually slightly stiffer when the fibres were aligned perpendicularly to the load rather than parallel to it. It is thought that this was because the pin transferred load directly to the fibres rather than compressing into the soft resin rich zone.

Ply Angle ϕ (Degrees)	Model SF Low Fidelity	Model DF High Fidelity
0	1.000	0.516
90	0.506	0.524

Table 4. Comparison of normalised equivalent stiffnesses for the two models and test cases.

Therefore, in a HYPER joint with a laminate with a high percentage of 0 and 90 degree plies ([0/90] dominant), it would be the 90 degree plies that transmit the highest loads between pin and laminate, not the 0 degree plies. The HYPER joint would also be considerably more compliant in a physical test than would be predicted using a low fidelity FE model.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

Conventional finite element modelling approaches homogenise CFRP plies and, as a result, do not have adequate geometric accuracy to model the in-plane fibre waviness that can be seen in HYPER joints. A high fidelity FE model of a unit cell was developed and successfully used to investigate two modelling strategies. It was found that, for a [0/90] dominant laminate, a homogenised model would transmit the greatest load through the 0 degree plies. However, when accounting for the fibre distortion and resin rich zones, the load transmitted through the 90 degree plies would be slightly higher than that carried by the 0 degree plies.

Therefore, if a laminate has a high percentage of [0/90] plies, a low fidelity model would not yield accurate results and the peak stresses would be artificially high (up to 67%). Failure would initiate prematurely and in the wrong locations within the laminate. The true stress concentrations would not be accounted for when using a low fidelity model.

Work is ongoing to refine the pre-processor to increase computational efficiency. Work will also focus on three dimensional high fidelity models so that inter-ply coupling and other stacking sequences (such as ± 45 degree plies) could be investigated. In addition, failure criterion will also be introduced. The ultimate goal is to upscale these high fidelity unit cell models to a macro-level (whole coupon) model and develop an efficient multi-scale optimisation tool for HYPER joints.

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